

Maintaining and updating food composition datasets for multiple users and novel technologies: Current challenges from a UK perspective

M. H. Traka* and P. M. Finglas*[†]

*Food Databanks National Capability, Quadram Institute Bioscience, Norwich Research Park, Norwich, UK;

[†]EuroFIR AISBL, Brussels, Belgium

Abstract

The UK national food composition dataset, maintained at the Quadram Institute Bioscience, is a valuable national resource for a variety of users. The UK has a long history of compiling and utilising food composition data, which started for the specific purpose of understanding war-time nutrition, and is now fundamental to multiple areas of research, policy, food manufacturing and consumer behaviour. The rise of mHealth technologies has brought food and nutrition data direct to the consumer and presents new challenges for food data compilers relating to coverage of foods and nutrients, and accessibility and transparency of data. In addition, emerging efforts in sustainable food production, changing diets and the ever-increasing burden of non-communicable diseases requires an integrated approach that will span the agri-food, nutrition and health space. In order to achieve this, there needs to be continued efforts in food data standardisation, international collaboration and stronger emphasis in making food and nutrition data FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable). The UK national food composition data and the emerging initiatives in food and nutrition it supports are playing an important role in the future development of healthy and sustainable UK diets.

Keywords: dietary intake, food composition data, food labelling, mHealth, nutrition, public health

Introduction

Tables and databases of food composition data underpin our understanding of the fundamental relationships between diet and health. The data are usually compiled at a national level, but tailored datasets do exist for

specific purposes or to contain particular types of data, such as data on branded foods. They are used across multiple fields including dietetics, food technology, biomedical research, public health policy (Finglas *et al.* 2014) and are essential for the development of nutrition-based health programmes and research (Marconi *et al.* 2018). The information contained within food composition datasets can be applied in the assessment of health and nutritional status at the individual, regional, national and international level (Church 2006).

Correspondence: Maria H. Traka, Deputy Head of Food Databanks National Capability, Quadram Institute Bioscience, Norwich Research Park, Norwich, Norfolk, NR4 7UQ, UK.
E-mail: maria.traka@quadram.ac.uk

As a leading example, the UK Composition of Foods Dataset (Roe *et al.* 2015; PHE 2019a), which is the complete national food composition dataset in the UK, has evolved progressively over time and has been instrumental in the delivery of significant research outputs across the fields of food, nutrition and health. These include the government's *National Diet and Nutrition Survey (NDNS)* which informs policy on dietary advice, encourages nutritional awareness and promotes healthy lifestyles nationally (PHE 2019b). The UK Composition of Foods Dataset also makes a significant contribution to capacity development in food data compilation internationally (Ene-Obong *et al.* 2019), and is essential for meeting food labelling requirements, standards and regulations within the UK.

In their simplest form, food composition datasets are published as tables in traditional hard copy; McCance and Widdowson's *The Composition of Foods*, now in its 7th Edition (MW7, Finglas *et al.* 2015), remains one of the most highly cited reference works for food and nutrition. However, increasingly these datasets are being made available in the form of detailed electronic databases that provide standardised information on nutrient components alongside supporting documentation about the source of the values. Food composition data need to be regularly updated to account for potential influential changes in products and practices, including: changes in animal/crop production (*i.e.* new animal breeds, changes to husbandry practices, new crop varieties); new fresh, ambient, frozen and processed foods introduced to the diet/market; changes to the nutrient content of existing foods; foods reformulated in line with government public health initiatives (including reductions in the amount of fat, *trans* fatty acids, saturates, sugar and salt); and changes to how foods are prepared and cooked at home.

The UK Composition of Foods Dataset: A brief history

A flow chart summarising the history of the development of the UK Composition of Foods Dataset since 1929 is shown in Figure 1. Over the last 80 years, seven printed versions of the tabulated datasets have been published along with 12 supplements, each containing extensive data on specific food groups (Box 1).

Robert Plimmer published the first systematic British food composition tables in 1921 (Plimmer 1921), including data on water, ash, protein, carbohydrates and fat in 900 foods. However, since then, the names

Box 1 The 12 supplementary reports available for the UK Composition of Foods

- Amino acids and Fatty acids, supplement (1980)
- Immigrant Foods, supplement (1985)
- Cereals and Cereal Products, supplement (1988)
- Milk Products and Eggs, supplement (1989)
- Vegetables, Herbs and Spices, supplement (1991)
- Fruit and Nuts, supplement (1992)
- Vegetable Dishes, supplement (1992)
- Fish and Fish Products, supplement (1993)
- Miscellaneous Foods, supplement (1994)
- Meat, Poultry and Game, supplement (1995)
- Meat Products and Dishes, supplement (1996)
- Fatty Acids, supplement (1998)

of Professor Robert McCance and Dr Elsie Widdowson have become synonymous with food composition tables. The first edition of McCance and Widdowson's *The Chemical Composition of Foods* was published in 1940 and emphasised that 'a knowledge of the chemical composition of foods is the first essential in the dietary treatment of disease or in any quantitative study of human nutrition' (McCance & Widdowson 1940). The book was updated in 1946 to include new war-time dishes and ingredients that reflected rationing and highlighted the importance of understanding nutrient composition of the diet for ensuring the health of the population and the troops during the war.

The first tabulated datasets were driven by food supply studies and, since then, updated due to increasing international trade, market entry of ethnic foods and dishes, new functional ingredients and process technologies. The food supply chain has changed significantly and the variety of processed foods available today is far removed from the foods listed in the initial food composition tables (Krines & Finglas 2006). Public Health England (PHE) supports the update and maintenance of the UK dataset for application in public health initiatives, including the NDNS. The UK dataset has been managed by food compilers based in Norwich since the publication of the 4th Edition of McCance and Widdowson's *The Composition of Foods* in 1978 (Paul & Southgate 1978), and is currently the responsibility of the Food Databanks National Capability (FDNC) at the Quadram Institute Bioscience (QIB). The most recent printed edition (MW7), containing a subset of the full UK dataset, was produced in 2015 (Finglas *et al.* 2015) by authors from the FDNC, in association with PHE, and published by the Royal Society of Chemistry.

Figure 1 Timeline for evolution of the UK Composition of Foods Dataset from 1929. [Colour figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

Current UK food composition data complies with European standards and is integrated into a unified platform hosted by the European Food Information Resource (EuroFIR) (EuroFIR 2020). EuroFIR is a non-profit international association based in Belgium, involving food compilers from 27 countries that was founded in 2009 as a result of an EU Framework Programme 6 (FP6) Network of Excellence project that included compilers at the QIB. Its mission is to develop and promote harmonisation of high-quality food composition data and to foster co-operation and community development within compiler organisations (www.eurofir.org).

How is data available in the UK?

In addition to the MW7 book form (1180 foods, 47 nutrients), the Composition of Foods Integrated Dataset (CoFID) brings together for the first time all the available current data in a single, consolidated, electronic format. The current CoFID (release 2019) is available, free to all, as a Microsoft Excel workbook download [3303 foods, 275 nutrients (including fatty acids per 100 g fatty acids)], and through a searchable web tool (FDNC 2020). The 2019 online release includes data from the most recent Fruit and Vegetable Survey (PHE 2017b), adding new analysis for 62

foods. Foods analysed within the last 10 years have included analysis of fibre using the American Associate of Analytical Chemists (AOAC) method. This was particularly important for analysis of fruit and vegetables in 2017 due to the recommendation by the Scientific Advisory Committee on Nutrition (SACN) in its *Carbohydrates and Health* Report (SACN 2015). Sampling, preparation and cooking procedures used in the survey were updated to better reflect current consumer trends (e.g. steamed asparagus, roasted sweet potatoes) and the survey also included new information on edible portions for 27 foods. A future CoFID release will contain new analysis of raw and cooked cuts of pork to update the previous values from 1992 (Pinchen *et al.* 2020).

The online web tool (Figure 2), which was prepared in close partnership with PHE, allows users to search for the nutrient content of foods and recipes in CoFID and includes previously unpublished nutrient-specific comments, which present the origin of the values allowing users to make a more informed judgement about the suitability of the data for their intended purpose. This search tool brings the UK in line with other countries that have similar food data resources and

increases accessibility to users, particularly the public, who have previously indicated that they found it difficult to find information in the full Excel download. Future efforts are underway to provide an Application Programming Interface, known as API that will increase accessibility of the UK data for app developers and other software developers.

Comparison with 37 other national food composition datasets that are available via the EuroFIR FoodEXplorer tool (Figure 3) shows that the UK dataset includes the third biggest number of different food items (3303), that also includes a substantial number of nutrient component values (260 723) demonstrating the wide range of information available per food.

Who uses food composition data?

Food composition data are the fundamental evidence base for nutrition science and extensively used in the public health domain. Additionally, advances in information technologies, the increasing use of 'big data' and the development of mobile devices and wearables is fostering the exploitation of food composition data in new ways. The UK composition data is utilised by

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Food Databanks National Capability extended dataset based on [PHE's McCance and Widdowson's Composition of Foods Integrated Dataset](#)

SEARCHING FOR: "FIG"

Search for Food

		per 100g						
Code	Name	Energy (kJ)	Energy (kcal)	Fat (g)	Water (g)	Carbohydrate (g)	Sugars (g)	Protein (g)
11-805	Fig Rolls	1532	363	10.6	13.7	66.8	43.8	4.2
14-395	Figs, ready-to-eat, semi-dried	790	186	1.2	27.5	43.3	43.3	3.1
14-092	Figs, whole fruit, dried	967	227	1.6	16.8	52.9	52.9	3.6
14-093	Figs, dried, stewed with sugar	612	143	0.8	50.1	34.3	34.3	1.9
14-094	Figs, dried, stewed without sugar	537	126	0.9	53.8	29.4	29.4	2.0
14-091	Figs, whole green fruit, raw	185	43	0.3	84.6	9.5	9.5	1.3

Email: fdnc@quadram.ac.uk

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Figure 2 Screenshot showing the search results for 'fig' from the Composition of Foods Integrated Dataset (CoFID) online search tool, listing the different foods returned from the search and a summary of their main proximates. Further detailed information is given by clicking on selected food codes. [Colour figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

Figure 3 Chart showing the number of different foods (in black) and their total nutrient components (in grey) in the top 15 datasets from FoodEXplorer (EuroFIR 2020). UK data include total publicly available data.

a variety of users, both nationally and internationally, across a range of different fields (Figure 4), which makes the provision of new and updated UK data and knowledge on food composition essential to support these areas, as highlighted below.

Public health

Food composition data is used in the field of public health to understand the potential health impacts of changes in food composition and consumption. PHE is responsible for maintaining up-to-date data on the nutrient content of the UK food supply and it incorporates CoFID data into its nutrient databank for use in dietary assessment surveys to calculate nutritional intake values, and particularly to support the rolling programme of the *NDNS*. Regular updates to CoFID allow improved accuracy of intake assessments, better reflecting the diversity of foods now consumed in the UK, and current trends in preparation. Outputs from these surveys inform guidelines and policy documents that promote healthy eating and a reduction in chronic disease rates in the UK. The SACN report on *Saturated Fats and Health* (SACN 2019) is a recent

example of a policy document based on *NDNS* results, and thus on CoFID data. Each updated publication of CoFID provides revised and improved data for end users which, in turn, translates into better informed public health policies and monitoring.

Industry and innovation

From an industry perspective, it is essential that communication of nutritional information to the consumer is clear and accurate, which is aided by the availability of robust food composition data. Specifically, the food industry and food service providers use composition data to underpin implementation of food information regulations, reformulate foods, support nutrition and health claims and for the development of digital diet-related health tools.

Businesses selling pre-packed foods are required by the EU to include nutritional information on the packaging (EU 2011). For small food producers, who make up 97% of the UK's 7290 food and drink businesses (Food & Drink Federation 2019), laboratory analysis of nutrient composition for their products is both complex and costly. However, calculating nutritional

Figure 4 Schematic showing the different users of food composition data.

composition using food composition tables (such as CoFID) is an acceptable alternative and can be carried out using online tools. However, random or systematic errors in database use could occur leading to the need for training and accreditation schemes for producers of labelling software. While correct use of food composition data for labelling requires some expert advice, it is still a cost-effective alternative and ensures that small businesses have access to services that can help them produce compliant food labelling (Department of Health 2017). Access to food composition data has also encouraged innovation in the food industry (Roodenburg & Leenen 2007). For example, it has enabled manufacturers and retailers to proactively produce products with improved nutritional profiles to help meet government dietary recommendations.

Diet and health professionals

Food composition datasets are important resources within the clinical setting (*i.e.* for doctors, GPs, dietitians, nutritionists and health professionals). The information in the datasets allows clinicians to provide care and advice that is based on research, dietary monitoring and evidence-based development of

healthier products. McCance and Widdowson's *The Composition of Foods* remains a primary text resource for dietetic and nutrition training in the UK; 4379 copies of the 7th Edition of have been sold by the Royal Society of Chemistry since it was published in 2015.

Food composition data is used to develop therapeutic diets for people who need to carefully manage their nutrient intake for medical reasons. When data compilers work with specialist users of composition data, it is possible to create tailored datasets and to identify gaps in the current dataset. FDNC recently worked with renal dietitians (Hannah *et al.* 2018) in a study that identified limitations in the current UK phosphorous composition data that has serious implications for the accurate development of phosphorous-restricted diets, which form a central part of long-term care for many of the approximately 3 million people in the UK that have chronic kidney disease (Kidney Care UK 2020).

Research and academia

Nutritional data feed directly into multi-disciplinary national and international research projects in the

areas of epidemiology, diet and health, and emerging research infrastructure initiatives. The most common application of food composition data in research is in combination with dietary intake data to provide estimates of nutritional exposure or intake, required for both large-scale epidemiology studies and for smaller interventions. Composition data is also essential in the development of test diets or products for intervention studies. Research projects and collaborations also help to identify novel methods of utilising composition data and new applications for compiler knowledge. An example is the Nutritools website (www.nutritools.org) developed and tested by UK compilers and a wider network of UK nutrition epidemiological centres that allows researchers to select dietary assessment tools appropriate for their research and to find appropriate food nutrient data and recipes (Hooson Jzh *et al.* 2019).

Food data compilers also provide expertise in the creation of new food databases, which may capture data on new food components, for example, bioactives (Plumb *et al.* 2017), or repurpose traditional nutrient composition information, for example, food waste (Pinchen *et al.* 2019). UK compilers work with their international counterparts to produce harmonised, standardised data, and these initiatives often start as research projects, such as the EuroFIR Network of Excellence under EU FP6 (Westenbrink *et al.* 2016). New research initiatives such as the Food, Nutrition and Health Research Infrastructure, developed from the outcomes of the *RICHFIELDS* project (Maringer *et al.* 2018), and large-scale projects such as the *Food and Nutrition Security Cloud Horizon2020* project (www.fns-cloud.eu/) are reshaping how food and nutrition data are stored, shared and utilised across Europe. Food composition data will form an integral part of any future over-arching research infrastructure or federation of food data.

Consumers

Food labelling regulations, Internet resources and mobile apps have increased consumer awareness of, and access to, nutritional information. Many consumers use these data to make informed choices about their diet and this transparency of information has, in combination with public health policies, led to food manufacturers creating healthier products. A primary driver for the introduction of the new online searchable web tool for CoFID (FDNC 2020) was frequent requests from members of the public for a quick and reliable means to look up

information for a single food. The tool is freely available for all to use, and eliminates the need to download the full CoFID dataset. The mHealth market, which is based on digital technologies, particularly mobile apps and wearable devices, has seen significant expansion in the last 10 years. Many of the apps and devices aim to improve consumer nutrition and health, and often use a food composition database, though the source and quality of the data is sometimes unclear. In the personalised nutrition market in particular, companies are offering apps, web services and genetic testing, but there is currently limited regulation on the offerings. Consumer trust in these apps is generally low due to the lack of transparency about the source of information or robustness of the supporting science. The *Quisper* project (Quisper ASBL 2020), funded by EIT-Food and co-led by the FDNC, is a personalised nutrition platform attempting to address this issue by offering app developers access to scientifically robust services and data, and by evaluating personalised nutrition apps for scientific quality. This will in turn bring scientifically validated nutrition advice directly to consumers, and help them to make better dietary choices, thereby promoting healthy lifestyles.

Consumers do not need to access data themselves to benefit from high-quality food composition datasets. The general public will also benefit from the utilisation of food composition data by the other users described in this section, whether as part of improved medical care, public health policies, greater selection of foods on the market or via the diet and health research that underpins most of these areas.

Current challenges and future directions – the importance of international collaboration, standardisation, staying current and data connectivity

Overcoming variation between food composition databases

Globally, around three-quarters of all countries have tables of national food composition data and this is growing (FAO 2017a); some examples of food composition datasets can be found online (EuroFIR 2020; Compilers' Toolbox™ 2020). However, some of these datasets vary considerably in scope and detail; inconsistencies between datasets from different countries currently make comparisons between countries very difficult (Finglas *et al.* 2017). With respect to the UK CoFID, detailed and standardised protocols are

followed for sampling (PHE 2017b), analysis and data documentation. This ensures consistency and accuracy across the data presented in CoFID. However, while it is possible for other countries to use values from the UK database if they have missing information, this cannot guarantee that the values are directly comparable to the corresponding food items consumed in the other country (Roe *et al.* 2013).

To overcome this challenge, UK food data compilers are working with international compilers to create validated and standardised food composition databases, ensuring data can be easily retrieved and compared across countries in support of pan-EU food and health studies. This international participation and co-operation is being achieved via EuroFIR and the International Network of Food Data Systems (INFOODS). As a key member of the EuroFIR Association, UK compilers contribute to some of the EuroFIR working groups that address all issues related to standardisation of food composition data (Aggregation of Data, Laboratories, Recipe Calculation, Documentation, FoodCASE, Branded Foods). Via the activities of its members, EuroFIR has contributed to the development and coding implementation of FoodEx2, a European food classification system, as well as the development of food composition tools such as FoodCASE (a food composition data management tool) and FoodEXplorer (a query tool of food composition data across 37 countries) (Finglas *et al.* 2014). INFOODS (FAO 2017b) is a worldwide network of food composition experts aiming to improve the quality, availability, reliability and use of food composition data.

As experts in food composition data methods and best practice, the UK compilers have also been involved in a number of training schemes, knowledge exchanges and capacity development drives including in Africa and the Eastern Mediterranean Region (EMR) where food composition datasets are of varying quality and not always representative of local diets. Following training workshops held in these regions (supported by the UK Research and Innovation Global Challenges Research Fund) action plans for improving national and regional datasets have been initiated. Six harmonised datasets from Africa and the EMR are now freely available online within FoodEXplorer (EuroFIR 2020). These databases have the potential to enable local scientists to improve nutritional education and standardisation; they are also supporting work to implement the World Health Organization's nutrition and health policies in the region (reducing fat, sugar and salt).

Keeping up-to-date

There has been a considerable increase in the number of manufactured foods available at supermarkets, local retailers and the Internet over recent years. The infrequency of McCance and Widdowson data updates has meant that composite data cannot keep pace with frequent product reformulations and developments that occur within the manufacturing and retail sector. Thus, published food composition data may not be the most accurate way to determine nutritional data for composite foods. CoFID predominantly contains data for 'generic' foods that reflect nutritional information for 'typical' and 'average' products, based on detailed analytical information on a variety of foods as well as some calculated values for composite dishes. To reflect average UK consumption, the sampling methods used to generate analytical data account for market share of retail outlets, origin, 'quality' (*e.g.* premium vs. economy), food service and availability.

Although retailers find food composition data an invaluable resource, there is an increasing need and expectation for 'real-time' data (Howie 2015), which has prompted the development of other methods of data collection. Recently, the use of data mining methods such as web crawling and scraping has allowed projects, working in a similar manner to price comparison sites, to collect nutrition data on 'branded' products rapidly via retailer websites [*e.g.* FoodDB (Harrington *et al.* 2019), Open Food Facts (Open Food Facts 2020)]. These 'big data' approaches are certainly faster and cheaper than construction of standard food composition databases and provide great opportunities to enhance our capacity for capturing nutritional information of foods. There is a useful complementary role for these approaches in monitoring and analysing potentially frequent changes in nutritional formulation of products, but there is a long way to go if we are to ensure the transparency and accuracy of such information; currently, there is no requirement to disclose the origin of the values presented online. The biggest limitation of such approaches is that they can only provide information on a limited number of nutrients, namely the nutrient declaration data (energy, fat, carbohydrates, protein, salt), as opposed to the broader range of nutrients (including vitamins, minerals, individual fatty acids) that are freely available in the UK CoFID. This is significant to nutritionists who need to determine the nutritional quality of the diet at the individual level, and public health officials who assess the nutritional requirements of a population. Although efforts have

started to develop methods that can calculate an expanded nutritional profile based on the limited information provided by the manufacturer on the label, such gap filling is still in its infancy and will need to be tested. Furthermore, supermarket purchases do not account for all our food purchases; more than one quarter (27.1%) of adults and one fifth of children eat food from out-of-home food outlets, not including schools, at least once a week (PHE 2017a). To be robustly useful, food data acquired through data mining must ensure that it follows internationally accepted nomenclature and standards, which allows food data standardisation worldwide (e.g. EuroFIR standards), in order to maximise its use. This would allow crowd-sourced branded food data and industry-independent generic data to be combined to improve assessment of diets.

Shaping the future use of food composition data

Food composition data are used to enable the development and application of new validated tools and methodologies for dietary assessment. It will therefore be a central component in the emerging initiatives designed to draw together multiple domains of diet and health research, combined with sustainable food systems research, to create over-arching supporting structures for improved research and collaboration. UK compilers are working with other UK and leading European centres to develop the framework for a wider Food, Nutrition and Health Research Infrastructure (FNH-RI), which will provide a technical platform to bring together data, tools and resources to facilitate inter-disciplinary and multi-national research and exponentially transform the uptake and exploitation of food composition data. Web-enabled food composition platforms for nutrients and bioactive compounds are under development that will facilitate links to dietary assessment tools, food information, and consumer lifestyle and behaviour data, to promote data compatibility, sharing and reuse through making food and nutrition data FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable).

Research infrastructures are an increasingly important part of the research landscape, enabling greater collaboration, efficiency, harmonisation and transparency in research, which in turn benefits the consumer, industry and other stakeholders. For example, the *Food and Nutrition Security Cloud* project (www.fns-cloud.eu/) is an ambitious technical project that will evaluate a broad spectrum of food-related data and then create and test a cloud-based resource for

federating and exploiting it. Part of this project will be dedicated to understanding the particular challenges associated with combining food and microbiome data. Gut health and microbiome profiling are areas of rapid research expansion, and therefore understanding how food data can contribute to this domain is a current priority.

Conclusions

National food composition data underpin our understanding of the fundamental relationships between diet and health, support public health policy on dietary advice and encourage nutritional awareness. This is reflected in the varied nature of users of national food composition data, which include food and health professionals, public health users, academics, and in particular epidemiologists and diet and health researchers, as well as individual consumers and industry. The UK Composition of Foods Dataset has a long history of evolving to address changing diets and external circumstances (i.e. change in purchasing habits, change in products and practices, emerging technologies). Modern expectations require information to be instantly accessible, which can create challenges in relation to food composition data. Generation of high-quality analytically-based food composition data take time to compile and is relatively expensive but such data provide a robust and comprehensive range of the UK foods, which can serve as the benchmark for the nutritional composition of the UK's food supply. Nevertheless, emerging needs in public health and in sustainable food production require collective standardisation efforts and better structures to allow connecting food composition data with health and food systems data. The complexity of this should not be underestimated but the UK is already well placed to begin to address some of these issues.

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